

D2.2. Multi-assessment of impacts, trade-offs and framework conditions

Social Acceptance Section

List of Acronyms

CAP	Common Agricultural Policy
CF	Circular Fertiliser
EU	European Union
GHG	Greenhouse gas
IWW	Industrial wastewater
LCSA	Life Cycle Sustainability Assessment
NIMBY	Not In My Backyard
NGO	Non-Governmental organization
PSILCA	Product Social Impact for Life Cycle Assessment
SME	Small and medium enterprise
UWW	Urban wastewater

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Executive summary

The acceptance of circular fertilisers is cardinal in the adoption of a circular economy focus on Europe. The present research is sustained three surveys conducted to three key stakeholders: farmers, fertiliser producers and local administration. The answers are surveyed to understand the necessary conditions for the proper adoption of circular fertiliser in the European farms.

For this purpose, eight questions regarding social acceptance dimensions and seven questions related to legitimacy theory are used to release qualitative information about social behaviours only in the farmer's case. The answers are assessed to understand the current status of acceptance and legitimacy of the circular fertilisers, studying farmers' concerns, preferences, trustworthiness and willingness to change to these circular alternatives among their fields.

In the social acceptance of farmers towards circular fertilisers, policymakers expose a weak institutional capacity, leading to a low socio-political force. The market acceptance is promising whether concerns and preferences of farmers are mitigated. As ending, the community acceptance remains neutral according to this study, even though good opinions and positive attitudes are found. Evaluating the legitimacy, not a clear trend is found in the pragmatic legitimacy of circular fertilisers. Also, an unstable normative legitimacy is exposed due to a lack of trust in politicians that could materialise as a problem in the future. On the other hand, even though circular fertilisers do not offer an easy transition to the current scene, the cognitive legitimacy is promisingly positive due to a high taken-for-granted perception. Developing strategies should focus on addressing these shortcomings, using the above-mentioned pros.

1. Social acceptance assessment methodology

Public perception of circular fertilisers might be influenced by different factors including concerns about security, yields, and their environmental impact. As a consequence, it is fundamental to invest in public awareness viewing the benefits of these alternatives and addressing worries citizens might have.

Social considerations related to the implementation of innovations based on the use of waste are extremely complex owing to cultural trends and norms, lifestyle, income, diet, social mobility, habits, beliefs, educational level, and access to waste infrastructure (Agapios et al., 2020; Loizia et al., 2021; Voukkali et al., 2021). People will change when they can see a good reason to do so and when they perceive the relevance of the change. When dealing with large-scale change, it is often found that the behavioural route is the most effective. The issue of how we can shift the centre of gravity of the consumption model of individuals and cultures to embrace the concept of the circular economy is a key element in achieving change (Eskelinen et al., 2022).

With that clear, the followed method to assess the social acceptance of circular fertilisers is detailed below.

1.1.1. Design and data collection via surveys.

Social acceptance is a crucial factor for achieving social engagement. In the FER-PLAY context, three balanced surveys were developed to address farmers, fertiliser producers, and local administration/policymakers. Experts and stakeholders within the FER-PLAY project belonging to each of the mentioned groups were involved in this maturing process.

The surveys were spread among the target audience via the FER-PLAY Consortium contacts, events organised by the FER-PLAY partners, the project website (<https://fer-play.eu/>), etc. Moreover, it is worth mentioning that the surveys for end-users¹ and producers² were available in six languages (Dutch, English, French, German, Italian and Spanish) to reach as many users

¹ Dutch (<https://forms.office.com/e/YBcrQK7A2X>), English (<https://forms.office.com/e/0QHQEd42sv>), French (<https://forms.office.com/e/UmP36qsqqZ>), German (<https://forms.office.com/e/sjWGXGSt5Z>), Italian (<https://forms.office.com/e/ZRk3BBrikD>), Spanish (<https://forms.office.com/e/EXBXDMzXrw>)

² Dutch (<https://forms.office.com/e/eK8HF7sPnp>), English (<https://forms.office.com/e/gmp2j84ikA>), French (<https://forms.office.com/e/JiTURd0N6>), German (<https://forms.office.com/e/77rqq1w0F3>), Italian (<https://forms.office.com/e/85BsPRtadt>), Spanish (<https://forms.office.com/e/VBse534HUJ>)

as possible; whereas, the survey led to local administration/policymakers³ were only available in Dutch, English and French. Although the online version was the most recurrent, the consortium strived to achieve respondents in person, minimizing mistakes. In this way, the surveys were also publicised among working groups, key events, conventions and focus groups; organised by FER-PLAY partners.

Sampling size: A total of 360 answers were collected for farmers, 86 for fertiliser producers and 8 for policy makers.

1.1.2. Result analysis

Quantitative analysis was performed on three different stakeholders. The survey was performed throughout Europe, applying the same questions regardless of the countries, but allowing to segment the results by countries.

1. Descriptive analysis.

A quantitative study was carried out; Microsoft PowerBI® and Microsoft Excel® were used to develop graphs and tables from raw data.

2. Discussion using a qualitative approach.

The outcomes of the previous analysis were evaluated for discussion.

3. Assessment of the social acceptance and legitimacy.

This last assessment was applied only to the farmers' group.

The assessment and interpretation of the results were performed qualitatively. Eight questions were used as a guide to feed the sections and subsections related to social acceptance and other seven questions were posed to assess the social legitimacy of the circular fertilisers; more details below. These questions were developed by the authors and collected in Table 1 and Table 2. The 15 questions have the aim to bring insights about the conditions for a proper adoption of circular alternatives among the European Agrarian sector.

For social acceptance, Wüstenhagen et al. (2007) proposed fragmentation in three dimensions, contributing to the clarification of the literature: i) socio-political, ii) market and iii) community. At the same time, these dimensions can be split into sub-categories () as proposed by several authors (Sovacool et. al., (2012), Jones et al., (2017), Gordon et. al., (2022)). The definition of

³ Dutch (<https://forms.office.com/e/gg3Bp7vhkL>), English (<https://forms.office.com/e/T0CJmDGkuf>), French (<https://forms.office.com/e/whmUrKK9gL>)

these dimensions can be found bellow, right next to the question designed to evaluate the linked dimension.

Table 1. Sections and subsections selected to assess social acceptance of CF, next to the definition of each one and a question designed to carry out qualitative assessment of this subsection.

Section	Subsection	Definition	Question assessed
Socio political	Strong institutional capacity.	The capacity of countries to maintain ministries or specific departments that provide support with specific programmes of research and development dedicated to circular fertilisers	What are the perceptions of farmers about these institutions?
	Political commitment	Capability of public institutions to make circular fertilisers a highly visible topic	Are the communication channels among farmers an institution beneficial?
Market	Competitive properties of the new products	Circular fertiliser producers satisfy consumers' necessities successfully, with the local stock always available.	Are farmers' concerns and preferences addressed by the market?
	Mechanisms for information and feedback.	Reliable information related to policies, prices, and opportunities in the agrarian sector related to circular fertilisers flows properly among investors and end users.	Are farmers' communication channels with institutions and circular fertiliser producers reliable?
	Access to subsidies	End uses can be applied to funds or tax reduction fees for products produced with circular fertilisers.	Do the farmers feel the necessity of subsidizing these products?
Community	Prolific community/individual ownership and use	Circular fertilisers tend to be purchased and added to local fields.	Will farmers purchase local circular fertilisers on their business?

Section	Subsection	Definition	Question assessed
	Public participation in policymaking	End users and local community play a key role in circular fertilisers' policy.	Will farmers introduce legal trends to local agricultural policies?
	Recognition of externalities or positive public image	Circular fertilisers have a good public image.	Do farmers perceive these products as goods?

Another way to detect and address the drawbacks of circular fertilisers is to use the concept of legitimacy. This is a widespread idea in sociology, defined by the scholars as “a generalised perception or assumption that the actions of an entity are desirable, proper, or appropriate within some socially constructed system of norms, values, beliefs and definitions” (Johnson et al., 2006) Legitimacy does not study acceptance by targeting individual perceptions, but addresses sectorial and societal rules, norms, and conventions (Suchman & Mark C, 1995)

This concept has been applied to organisations (Scott W.R., 1995) and innovations (Binz & Truffer, 2017; Harris-Lovett et al., 2015), giving legitimacy to circular solutions. The sections and subsections of legitimacy vary among fields, as does social acceptance. Suchman's comprehensive work postulates three sections: i) pragmatic, ii) cognitive and iii) normative, with the later addition of the regulative section by Scott W.R. (2008).

Table 2. Sections and subsections of legitimacy selected to assess social acceptance, next to the definition of each one and a question designed to carry out the qualitative assessment of this subsection.

Section	Subsection	Definition	Question assessed
Pragmatic	Exchange	Evaluate the mainly benefits provided by the new alternative.	Are circular fertilisers ready to foster soil quality or farmers' concerns?
	Dispositional	Evaluate the degree of honesty and fairness in related organisations.	Is public administration fair? What about NGOs and farmers associations?
Cognitive	Comprehensive	It will be positive whether they are intertwined with pre-existing cultural beliefs. This is a passive cognitive idea that provides coherence to end users' perceptions.	Do circular fertilisers offer an easy transition in terms of training and legal limitations?
	Taken-for-granted	This is considered the most authoritative subsection on legitimacy. It takes advantage of the perception of a solution as inevitable, necessary, and therefore not questioned.	Is there any other option than circular fertilisers to improve soil quality?
Normative	Consequential	assesses the relevance of previous achievements that endorse a particular goal defined by normative rules.	There are different perception of circular fertilisers depending on the country?
	Procedural	It evaluates societal perception of a solution's effectiveness.	Are public administrations and producers developing business strategies according to the necessity of subsidies?
	Structural	Studies whether value chain actors can bring into the table consistent know-how. The existence of quality controls, toxicological essays, or business models of circular fertilisers is crucial for adding fairness to circular alternatives.	Can farmers' concerns be solved by the current status of the solutions provided by the producers?

2. Towards the social acceptance of circular fertilisers

Three surveys were conducted addressing three stakeholder groups, namely: fertiliser producers, local administration and end users. In this section, these surveys are analysed, extracting all the possible insights to understand the necessary conditions for the proper adoption of circular fertilisers. Then, a discussion based on the answers obtained through the most relevant survey questions is exposed, first using the widely known concept of acceptance, and lastly using the social concept of legitimacy. To the best of the authors knowledge, the legitimacy concept was never studied before in the circular fertilisers sector.

2.1. Stakeholders

2.1.1. Producers

In this studio the profile of surveyors was not equal to the actual average found on the agrarian sector in terms of gender, type of farming activities or fertiliser produced, among others. Non-representative sample was achieved and therefore, comparisons must be made from a qualitative and critical perspective.

Table 3. Number of answers received per country.

Country	Number of contestants	Percentage (%)
Portugal	3	3.5
Italy	53	61.6
Spain	19	22.1
Others *	11	12.8
Total	86	

*Other countries: Belgium, Denmark, Germany, Greece, Netherlands, Portugal and Serbia.

As seen in Table 3, Italy has the biggest representation, followed by Spain and other countries like Portugal. Because no country has a representative sample, the discussion was done without fragmentation.

Some brief questions were asked to classify the respondents, the survey includes a question related to their role in the company. Production manager seems to be the most frequent answerer of the survey, as seen in **Figure 1**, ensuring a good answer quality.

2.1.1.1. FERTILISER COMPANIES' PROFILE

In the present section, the company's profile is shown by splitting it into diverse general characteristics such as the number of operation years, age of the CEO or turnover of the business, among others. Then, a product related section is analysed, linking with an operational assessment of the companies. In the end, the authors studied the importance that fertiliser producing companies give to local perspectives and how they face the relation between those companies and end-users.

Figure 1. Role of respondents in the company.

This profile definition is cardinal to make critical comparisons between the sample of this study and the real European profile. It is important to bring into the table that this study do not show a representative sample.

2.1.1.1.1. General topics

As a starting point, it is important to bring into the table that 84% of the respondents develop circular products, and 6% sell both circular and synthetic products, as seen in **Figure 2**. As a consequence, the authors of this report can approximate the results extracted to the expected behaviour and characteristics of a circular fertiliser company.

Figure 2. Type of fertiliser produced by the surveyed companies

To continue, in **Figure 3** the CEO's age is shown. This data shows the ordinary fact that companies have senior CEOs. Younger companies with young CEOs might not be interested in conducting circular business.

Figure 3. Age range of the CEO of the surveyed company

The plot in **Figure 4** shows the years that the company is been operating. The graph clarify that the target audience of this survey are mature companies, with more than 15 years synthesising fertilisers.

To sum up, the respondents conform a sample of mature companies with senior CEO's.

Figure 4. Years of operation of the surveyed company.

Attending **Figure 5**, the turnover is split among different quantities. Only the interval of 500,000 and 1 million € seems to be the most recurrent sales of stock. Only the 19% response a turnover bigger than 20M €, accomplish the economic criteria of “big company” and therefore it is extracted that SMEs are the interested ones in producing on a circular way.

Figure 5. Turnover of the surveyed company

2.1.1.1.2. Product topics

In **Figure 6** the different CFs produced by companies are represented. Almost 66% of the answers belong to compost. Nevertheless, there are other value chains represented like the digestate, both the solid and the liquid phases.

Figure 6. Circular fertilisers produced by the companies that answer they produce those products.

Other products like struvite or bio ammonium sulphate are not well represented. Even using waste sources as a starting raw material, their production is still no worthy due to the expensiveness and lack of optimised production pathways. More research is needed to boost these products.

Figure 7. Main feedstock used for producing the circular product.

By definition, CFs need to use by-products as a starting material. Related to feedstock, **Figure 7** represent the most frequent starting materials by companies. The most repeated option is biowaste due to the compost production, but also 20% of companies use raw sewage. Tonnes of nutrient recovery study cases have already been reported by researchers. One point to keep in mind is the necessity to carry out toxicological analysis to the final products.

2.1.1.1.3. Operational topics

Figure 8. Where the fertiliser producer companies a) sell their products and b) buy their feedstock.

Moving to the action plan of the company, the survey allow the writers to distinguish between different companies, depending on the feedstock provider and the customer location. **Figure 8b** shows the feedstock provider location. Among the less frequent answers were international and national, showing an increasing trend when providers are nearest to the production plant. The most common answer is regional providers, accumulating 42% of the answers. Looking at the target customer, **Figure 8a** shows the same trend to prefer nearby markets.

In both cases self-consumption and self-production have the smallest adepts. Several ideas are extracted from there. At first sign the concept of circularity will approve those self-use modes. With the current state of the sector, according to the survey, producers cannot achieve proper results using these strategies. Other point to highlight is that is easier to produce with your own by-products that consume your own ones. Nevertheless, producers and farmers prefer to work with nearby products, being international markets a residual option

2.1.1.1.4. Importance of local focus

Taking a look at **Figure 9a**, the 40% report an overall growth between 3 and 10% of their net labour force in contrast with the last ten years. Only 26% experience a net growth in the number of employees lower than 3% in the past ten years. Those results are quite encouraging, showing a rise in sales among CF companies, who have more money to hire workers. Also, regarding **Figure 9b**, near 80% of the labour force is local. Therefore, this sort of businesses will boost local employment.

Figure 9. Representation of a) the overall variation in number of employees in the past ten years and b) the percentage of employees hired locally.

Also, in **Figure 10** is exposed that more than half of the fertiliser producers know about restrictions towards CF in their region or country. Due to the short-term market presence of several of these CF alternatives it is legitimate to see a reticent opinion in legal organisms.

Figure 10. Regulatory restrictions according to respondent's knowledge.

When the writers ask to the surveyors about their opinion of the common agricultural policy (CAP) a neutral opinion was highlighted. Even that the adepts to the CAP are bigger than the refusers, the difference is not measurable, as seen in **Figure 11**. The authors encourage to next policies to include local focus among regulation of circular fertilisers.

Figure 11. Opinion of the Common Agricultural Policy by respondents.

2.1.1.1.5. Farmers trustworthiness towards producers:

To conclude with this subscript, the authors of this document want to study deeper the business strategies of CF companies, analysing the relationship with their customers. In **Figure 12** is exposed that most of the companies consider important to take care of this relation and therefore have an agronomist on their personnel. There is a slight trend to prefer an outsourced advisor rather than internal employee.

Figure 12. Existence of specialised labour force in charge of the relationship among the fertiliser company and the end-users, highlighting if those workers are outsourced or ordinary employees.

In the previous chapter focus on end-user's perception of CF, the authors of this document highlight the fact that farmers do not trust in salespersons. In contrast, one of the most reliable sources are external advisors. Coming back to the above-mentioned graph, CF companies are adapting their sales "modus operandi" to this fact. On this way, they have a salesperson, but disaggregated to company decisions and reducing corporate extortion.

2.1.1.1.6. Conclusions of companies' profile

- Most of the respondent develop CF. Therefore, the ideas extracted in this chapter can be extrapolate to the circular fertiliser sector and not to the traditional fertiliser one.
- Young CEOs might not be particularly interested on producing CF.

- Companies with a turnover bigger than 20M € might not be particularly interested on producing CF.
- By far, biowaste as a feedstock and compost as a final product are the most repeated options among surveyors.
- CF producers prefer to buy the feedstock and sell their products as near as they can.
- The opinion about the CAP is neutral, exposing a lack of acceptance on this organisation.
- Farmers do not trust in producers and therefore companies are hiring outsourced salesperson to interact with end-users.

2.1.1.2. COMPANIES BEHAVIOUR

In order to understand the proper conditions for incorporating CF along the European fields, it is important to understand the requirements companies need to consider the production of CF attractive.

On this part of the descriptive analysis the authors go deeper along CF producers' companies, addressing the next topics: 1) at which level companies search for subsidies and which problems they found during the acceptance procedure of the grant; 2) the type of R&D investment they carry out; and 3) which sustainable reports and certificates the companies possess.

2.1.1.2.1. Subsidies

It is unavoidable to support companies that are introducing circular solutions among their catalogue of products. The EU is pushing towards this direction with subsidies. In the survey, a question was design to clarify if companies are aware of these subsidies and which regulatory level they check. The answers are presented in **Figure 13**. The 35% are not aware of any of these grants. Among the ones that are informed, the most recurrent answer is to check regional sources to subsidize their company. European institutions are the less consumed. This is noteworthy in order to keep addressing grants at national and regional levels. On this way the institutions will ensure a proper reception of this money.

Figure 13. Level of awareness exposed by companies regarding subsidies.

On the next figure, it is exposed the challenges that companies report during the acceptance procedure of subsidies. The 44% of contestants answer they do not have any trouble. Along the most frequent answers it is extracted "complex application requirements or documentation" and "lengthy processing times".

Figure 14. Challenges of difficulties found by companies while applying to subsidies.

2.1.1.2.2. Research and development

The EU invest several euros every year in R&D projects. The 2023-2024 working program for the Horizon Europe involves 13.5 billion euros. Nevertheless, this funds are not enough to involve all the companies in the sector and small and medium enterprises (SMEs) may not have enough specialised employees to accomplish the requirements to contest in these procedures. In **Figure 15a**, this reality is exposed, showing a 35% of participation in this short of projects.

Figure 15. Quantification of the number of enterprises that a) participated in R&D projects in the past ten years and b) have their own R&D plan

Even that a small percentage of companies apply to public R&D projects, **Figure 15b** shows that 82% of them do it internally. State of the art along CF is still changing and companies need specialized technicians to produce CF, in the same way that farmers mat require high educational level to apply them.

2.1.1.2.3. Sustainable reports and certificates:

Even that the European Union inform that sustainable reporting will be mandatory, at least form big enterprises, not many companies ask for external consistories for this service. It is still tough to find public reports on internet. On this line, is surprising to see that 61% of the surveyed companies measure metrics like sustainability and key-performance indicators (KPIs).

On this line, the survey wants to clarify the certifications achieved by companies. Those standards ensure the efficiency, quality and improvement of services provided by companies. The International Standard Organization (ISO) have several certifications depending on the particular field of operation of the company, being the most frequent standard achieved by companies, according to the survey. Other organisations like the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI) propose methods to carry out the above mentioned sustainable and performance reports. This

organisation was picked by two respondents, validating the idea that, even that companies execute metrics in sustainability, they do not follow a standard pathway. All these ideas are exposed in Figure 16.

Figure 16. Standards certificated by the surveyed companies

2.1.1.2.4. Conclusions of the corporate behaviour analysis

- Regional and national institutions should be in charge to distribute subsidies in order to maximise the number of applicants.
- CF companies perceived the acceptance procedure of subsidies as lengthy and complex.
- Even that not many companies apply to R&D projects, most of the companies develop their own R&D plan.
- More companies measure sustainability and performance of their processes than they do not. Nevertheless, the vast majority do not follow a standardised approach.

2.1.2. Local administration

As part of the social acceptance study, the opinion of public administration about CF was assessed. The respondents are for different countries of Europe, as exposed in Figure 17. Only one answer per country was collected, with the exception of Spain, which collected two.

Figure 17. Map exposing the countries that have at least one answer in the survey.

A small sample of eight respondents answer to the survey, highlighting the necessity to use alternative methods to tackle this particular stakeholders' group. In the scientific biography, several articles recovery recommendations to overcome these deviations (Peck, P. et. Al., (2009), Wolsink, M. (2018), Dermont, et.al., (2017)). Among other ideas, these articles show proper way of distribution of social acceptance surveys and the way to maximise the ideas extracted or the necessity to ensure the quality and reliability of science communication. Empowering scientists, public authorities, communicators and the public to engage meaningful dialogues are possible ideas to increase interest in those type of surveys. (European Commission, 2024). The proposed method might engage new adopters interested in printing their opinion on social acceptance surveys.

As a brief introduction, for this part of the analysis, the respondent's behaviour and capacity of acting will be exposed, highlighting their territory policy and ending with their opinion about the

current status of the CF producers' sector. On that way, the authors want to understand the interaction between farmers, producers and the concrete that joins those two pieces: policymakers.

2.1.2.1. RESPONDENTS' PROFILE:

Among the job positions, there are several ones. The role of technician is the only repeated one; three technicians answer the survey. Most of the respondents work on a regional level (Figure 18a), where their level of governance did not allow them to facilitate the adoption of circular fertilisers (Figure 18b).

Figure 18. Representation of a) the scope of work and b) the competences related to agrarian fields by respondents.

2.1.2.2. TERRITORY CHARACTERISTICS

In the chapter devoted to fertiliser producers, it arises the fact that these stakeholders truly push to a local focus of their business model. On this line, in **Figure 19** the writers of the present study scan the main challenges related to the sourcing of raw materials for the CF production, where the transportation expenses of by-products are repeated by half of the respondents. Indeed, the carriage cost are a big deal for public administration. According to the UNEP “Municipal solid waste generation is predicted to grow from 2.1 billion tonnes in 2023 to 3.8 billion tonnes by 2050. In 2020, the global direct cost of waste management was an estimated USD 252 billion”. Looking

at this data, it is clear that the waste treatment is an increasing sector and extracting revalorising these value chains will help to palliate the high transport costs.

Figure 19. Collection of the main challenges exposed by respondents related to the adoption of circular fertilisers in Europe.

2.1.2.3. OPINION OF THE STATUS OF CF SECTOR.

Regarding the challenges for the wider adoption of CFs, half of the respondents highlight the regulatory obstacles and the approval processes.

In **Figure 20**, the writers of the present study asked to the responders, as qualified workers of the public administration, which was their perception of the current regulatory environment related to CF production. Neither of the answers was hopeful. Complex permitting and compliance requirements are detected among a wide part of surveyors.

Figure 20. Graphs showing a) the significant barriers for the wider adoption and b) the perception of the regulatory environment found by respondents referring to circular fertilisers.

To conclude this assessment, the authors of the present study point out some initiatives that the responders' institutions are carrying out. The most repeated initiative to foster the promotion of CFs was to keep investing in R&D funds. This option is interesting because, with extra money, companies will have the chance to overtake the complex permitting and compliance requirements. The respondents also answer that their institutions are involved in educational activities, forums and bringing regulatory support, among others. All this information is collected in **Figure 21**. This dissemination part of the information is crucial, but it is cardinal to offer help and support all over the procedure. Otherwise, SMEs will not find attractive to produce those circular alternatives and in conclusion they will never end on the European soil.

Figure 21. Different initiatives carried by respondents to promote the use of circular fertilisers

2.1.3. End users

In this studio the profile of surveyors was not equal to the actual average found on the agrarian sector in terms of gender, type of farming activities or fertiliser produced, among others (Liboreiro, 2024).

Figure 22. Map exposing the countries that have at least one respondent in the survey

Even that the sample achieve in the survey's collection does not fit the European agrarian sector it is interesting to do a qualitative discussion. It is remarkable to take this fact into account to make comparisons.

Table 4. Number of answers received as a function of the countries.

Country	Number of contestants	Percentage (%)
Germany	125	34.7
Italy	87	24.2
Spain	123	34.2
Others *	25	6.9
Total	360	

* Other countries: Austria, Belgium, Ireland, The Netherland, Sweden, United Kingdom.

As observed in **Table 4**, the most frequent nationalities were Germany, Spain and Italy and, thus, the study case was performed for them. In addition, specific conditions were considered for each country.

As a brief introduction, a descriptive analysis was performed to the data extracted from the survey. For a better understanding, four subchapters are disclosed, tackling 1) the respondents' profile, 2) the willingness of using CF, 3) not-in-my-backyard (NIMBY) effect and supporting actions, ending with the 4) knowledge and trustworthiness among surveyors.

2.1.3.1. PARTICIPANTS' PROFILE

In the present section, the participants' profile is shown by splitting it into diverse characteristics such as age and gender, academic level, kind of farming, among others. This profile definition is cardinal to make comparisons on a critical perspective taking into account that this study does not show a representative sample.

2.1.3.1.1. Age and gender

The 61% were male and 39% female. Referring to the age, the average (assuming that the maximum age is 65 years old) of the contestants is 38 years old, in contrast with the 2020 rate of the EU, 45 years old (Popescu T. et. al., (2021)). The data from **Figure 23** shows a trend of youth

facing a new concern in fertilisers technology. The agrarian sector is still a sensitive environment in which less than 31% of women are found in the labour force *Farmers and the agricultural labour force - statistics - Statistics Explained*. (2020). This new labour force will include a rising representation of women.

Figure 23. Age range of the respondents.

The number of young farmers has significantly decreased from 3,3 million in 2005 to 2,3 million at 2023. Data from this year point that only 6% of the labour force in farms is younger than 35, with women representing only 4,9% of these workers (*HOME - European Congress of Young Farmers*, n.d.). This commitment to foster the EU's gender gap is addressed in the common agricultural policy (CAP): EU countries are required to consider the situation for women in rural areas when developing their rural development programmes (*Females in the Field - European Commission*, n.d.).

2.1.3.1.2. Academic level

Another fundamental detail to characterise the sample is the academic level of contestants. In the present study, performed between 2023 and 2024, the participants with a technical knowledge represented the 18.6%; whereas farmers without any related degree were 80%. The rest of the participants (1.4%) preferred not to answer.

According to Eurostat, in 2023 only 10,2% of farm managers held agricultural training, 17,5% had followed a basic training level, and the rest had only practical experience (*Farmers and the Agricultural Labour Force - Statistics - Statistics Explained*, 2020). This data is in harmony with the findings of the present studio.

Additionally, the survey included questions about respondents' knowledge on circular fertilisers to evaluate whether they are informed about the benefits of using them or not. In order to avoid any kind of biased opinion, the questions consisted of asking the participants which statement corresponded to the type of fertiliser: circular or mineral.

The **Figure 24** shows that in most part of the questions the correct answers (in green) are over the 50%. Two questions do not reach this criterion. Neither have more than 50% of incorrect answers but, as a social study, the consortium decides to include the non-answered questions as a lack of criteria and therefore, considered as partially incorrect.

Figure 24. Answers when farmers were asked to choose between circular or mineral fertilisers to the above questions, being the answers: 1) circular, 2) circular, 3) circular, 4) mineral, 5) mineral, 6) circular, 7) mineral and 8) circular.

All of the questions are cardinal for a proper understanding of the circular fertilisers. Only taking into account pros and cons of these products farmers will make a proper decision whether purchase or not circular alternatives to mineral fertilisers. In general, all the statements were answered with lack of determination. These lacks of knowledge might be consequence of an insufficient communication of public institutions of private producers. Recommendations for both stakeholders will be done in this document and along the duration of the FERPLAY project.

2.1.3.1.3. Type and size of farming

Figure 25. Type of farming practised by respondents

Referring to the type of agrarian production, farmers were asked what type of farming they had carried out, as observed in **Figure 25**. The 46.3% works on a conventional farm, whereas 42.2% works on an organic farm. The 11.5% is working on a transition state from conventional to organic. As a brief clarification, it is important to highlight that organic farms have additional requirements, apart from the type of fertiliser used.

In the survey, 27.7% of Italians and 5.7% of Spaniards carry out organic agriculture. It is important to point out that, in the studio study sample, only 2.4% of Italians are on transition, while 27.6% of Spanish contestants work on a transition farm. Most part of the German's surveys were collected on organic assemblies and conferences, leading to a 91% of organic farmers on the case studio.

One of the main objectives of the European Commission's Farm-to-Fork strategy is to encourage the development of organic farming areas, which should represent 25% of the EU's agricultural land by 2030. In Europe, the total organic area increased by 65% between 2012 and 2021. The

estimations show an estimated 15.9 million hectares (ha) in 2021, up from 14.7 million hectares in 2020 and 9.5 million in 2012. “The total organic area is the sum of the 'area under conversion' and the 'certified area'. Before an area can be certified as 'organic', it must undergo a conversion process, which may take two or three years depending on the crop. Therefore, data on areas 'under conversion' give an indication of the potential change in fully 'certified areas' according to the European Union [(Developments in Organic Farming - Statistics Explained, n.d.) Among the big four, France was the country with the biggest organic area in 2021 (2,775,671 Ha), followed by Spain (2,635,442 Ha), Italy (2,186,159 Ha) and Germany (1,601,316 Ha).

All the extracted data from the current study and the updated 2021 data from EUROSTAT are clustered in **Figure 26**. The bars show the percentages of organic and transition farms extracted from the survey. The remaining area should be traditional farms. This data can be contrasted by looking at the square points where the 2021 data of each country is represented.

Figure 26. Comparison between the organic and transition farming area found on the study and the organic area in 2021 in the three studied countries.

Data extracted from the conducted surveys clearly does not match the 2021 statistics. On the contrary shows:

- Decreasing interest among stabilised Spanish organic agrarians in circular fertilisers and loosing sense of collaboration due to a low answer rate in the survey, comparing to the other two countries.

- Interest among Spaniards to create organic farms, regarding the number of transition farms.
- Positive signs about the deadline of the farm-to-fork strategy, showing that might be possible to reach the 25% of organic area in 2030.

Figure 27. Type of fertiliser used by respondents in their fields

It is important to create new organic farms, but this might be an idyllic idea to increase this number up to 25% of the actual farming area. Even more, other key point of the farm to fork strategy is to reduce the number of used fertilisers up to 20%. Technical farmers are still sceptical about those numbers and propose alternative paths. Garmendia et. al. (Garmendia-Lemus et al., 2024) supports that European agrarian sector could potentially substitute 30% Fossil fertilisers with circular fertilisers. This strategy is supported by long term studies that even show a yield improvement while using circular fertilisers mixed with mineral ones (van der Bom et al., 2019).

2.1.3.1.4. Farming activities

One key aspect to understanding the surveys is farming activities. At this point, it is important to break down the data into cattle and farming. The agricultural production areas in Europe are divided into three main types: arable land crops (mainly cereals, root crops, fresh vegetables, green fodder, and industrial crops), permanent grassland (pastures and meadows), and permanent crops (fruit trees and berries, olive groves, and vineyards). This data is exposed in **Figure 28**.

Figure 28. Farming activities practiced by respondents

In the studio case, compared to the results, the 32% of contestants involves arable activities or related activities; the 24% answer carries mixed activities and the 7% live from activities related to livestock.

In addition, farm sizes fluctuate between 20 and 400 hectares (56.2%) and less than 20 hectares (38%). Only 5.9% work on a bigger field.

2.1.3.1.5. Fertiliser used by farmers

Regarding the fertiliser used (**Figure 27**), the most used is manure (33%), followed by a mix of synthetic and circular (26%). The 18% used a mix of circular fertilisers and the 14% agreed on using compost. Only 5% used synthetic products without the addition of any circular product. It is important to point out that many of the participants (41%, **Figure 25**) practiced an organic farming and, thus, these results show a large presence of circular fertilisers over the mineral ones.

There is a lack of information about the percentage of circular and mineral fertiliser used in the European fields. However, according to Eurostat (*Agri-Environmental Indicator - Mineral Fertiliser Consumption - Statistics Explained*, n.d.) there was a cumulative decrease of 6.4% between 2017 and 2021 in the consumption of mineral fertilisers.

2.1.3.1.6. Conclusions

- The fact that 51% of surveyors were under 34 years contrast with the lower average found in the EU. This youth have interest in circular fertilisers, matching the interests of the CAP.
- Technical farmers represent only the 18,2% of surveyors. This fact is disheartening due to the necessity of having extra experience in agrarian sciences to use properly organic fertilisers.
- Most of surveyors understand that circular fertilisers play a key role in improvement of soils quality. This assumption can be used to improve farmers acceptance.
- Organic farmers in Italy and Germany show more interest in organic event organised by European institutions. Currently, Spain has the 2nd largest organic area, behind France, but can lose its seat in the oncoming years.
- There is a cumulative decrease in the past years in the mineral fertilisers' consumption. This lack should be filled with circular ones.

2.1.3.2. WILLINGNESS OF USING CIRCULAR FERTILISERS

After getting an overview of the participants, other interesting issues were asked. In this way, the willingness of using circular fertiliser was evaluated by the respondents' preferences, their concerns and the circumstances (economic and production) under which they would use a circular fertiliser.

2.1.3.2.1. Importance of different characteristics of fertilisers when selecting them.

Respondents scored seven factors individually according to their preferences when choosing a fertiliser. The maximum concern was linked to the costs (75.5% agree this topic is very or extremely important), nutrients and composition associated with fertilisers (74.1% of surveyor answer very or extremely important), matching with studies carried out in 2019 with similar studies (Case et al., 2017; Egan. et. al., 2022; Smol, M., 2021; Laborda. et. al., 2023). This data point that subsidies must be economically appealing to attract new adopters to these new products, even if the circular fertiliser is well known by the farmer, as shown in a study tacking manure case (Hou, Y. et. al., 2018). Up to this moment, the estimations suggest that the price for a circular fertiliser at the 30–46% discount compared to the price of an equivalent mineral fertiliser would allow to maximise the market share of the product (Moshkin, E. et. al., 2023). On the other hand, it is interesting to mention that 53.4% and 43.7% selected as very important the option ease of use and currently used machinery, respectively. The first option referred to the application mode of the fertiliser; whereas the second one was link to the concern of using the same spreading machinery or they would need another one.

To end, the less important factors selected are the form (25,6% voted as non and slightly important) and the currently used machinery (14,5% voted non and slightly important). These findings are noteworthy because sociological studios point that farmers make rational decisions about fertiliser use, striving to maximise utility. This means that this chose is strongly linked to the perceptions of utility (Garmendia lemus et. al., 2024; Daadi, B. E., & Latacz-Lohmann, U., 2021). **Table 5** collect this information.

Table 5. Ranging importance when selecting a circular fertiliser of: form, ease of use, currently used machinery, nutrient and composition, cost, environmental aspects and production sustainability.

	Non important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Very important	Extremely important
Form	7.5%	18.1%	28.9%	33.6%	10.6%
Ease of use	0.3%	5.1%	22.8%	53.4%	18.4%
Currently used machinery	2.5%	12.0%	30.0%	43.7%	11.8%
Nutrient content and composition	0.3%	2.2%	23.5%	35.8%	38.3%
Cost	0.0%	3.4%	21.2%	36.6%	38.9%
Environmental aspects	0.3%	7.5%	31.3%	35.8%	24.7%
Production sustainability	0.8%	7.0%	24.4%	44.7%	22.8%

Farmers rely on their own perceptions and opinions. Their perception of utility is influenced by their social network and, in turn, affect their attitude towards CIRCULAR FERTILISER. Social networks and expert technicians' acceptance play a crucial role in shaping farmers' intentions (Garmendia lemus et. al., 2024).

2.1.3.2.2. Participants' concerns

After evaluating the importance aspects of circular fertilisers, the respondents were asked about their concerns on fertilisers characteristics related to price (**Figure 29b**), their performance (**Figure 29a**), environmental impact (**Figure 30a**) and sustainability (**Figure 30b**). Additionally, the results on the participants' belief that circular fertiliser enhance soil health are also shown (**Figure 31**).

Linking with the farmers' perception of important factors of fertilisers, the concern about cost is shown. The vast majority of the participants show concern about this question, as represented in

Figure 29b. Only 4% of respondents are non-concerned about the cost of the fertiliser, and 14% are just slightly concerned. This point is in consonance with the results shown in **Error! Reference source not found.**, showing a characteristic to be aware off, as highlighted for previous authors.

Figure 29. Concern about a) the performance and b) price of the purchased circular fertiliser.

The 30% of participants considered as moderately concerned about the fertiliser performance. This points out that a significant fraction of respondents was not too much worried whether the fertiliser correctly yield. Taking a look at the above-mentioned preferences, it is clear that customers are concerned about other technical factors like the prize or the nutrient composition. Yield is an end-point, and farmers are concerned about the middle states of its processes.

Similarly, the majority of participants (40%) were moderately concerned on the environmental impacts caused by the fertiliser used (**Figure 30**). This perception of safety might be explained due to a proper policy regulation in circular fertilisers. One example is the arising analysis of circular products coming from waste by-products. Those waste sources come up with big amounts of microplastics and is being one of the reasons of the previous bad reputation of these fertilisers (Estoppey, N. et. al., 2024). In 2019 the Regulations (EC) No 1069/2009 and (EC) No 1107/2009 started setting new rules (Vivienne H., 2019). Even that, up to these days the imposition of doing quality tests to those products are still on construction, farmers might perceive these policies as reliable.

Figure 30. Concern on a) the environmental impact and b) the sustainability of the circular fertiliser

On the contrary, **Figure 30** displays that most of participants were concerned about the sustainability of their fertilisers (67% answer they are very or extremely concerned); whereas, 72% considered that circular fertilisers strongly or surely enhance soil health (**Figure 31**). Both an improvement on sustainability and soil health reduces the environmental impacts and, thus, it is remarkable that these impacts are perceived for the participants.

Figure 31. Belief on circular fertilisers enhance soil health.

The shown differences in **Figure 30** might disclose a lack of information or clarity to identify that both concepts are interlinked as the less environmental impacts, the more sustainable is the fertiliser. This could be considered as a hotspot to be addressed by both product developers and policymakers. However, this is another issue found in the present study as shown later, in the point Trustworthiness.

2.1.3.2.3. Circumstance of choosing a circular fertiliser

In this last point, the local production (**Figure 32**) and the willingness of using a circular fertiliser (**Figure 32**) are shown. Finally, the probability of participants to switch their current fertiliser to a circular one is also displayed (**Figure 34**).

Figure 32 shows that the local production of a circular fertiliser is important for the 59% of the surveyed people. However, it is not easy to find it as observed in **Figure 32**; where 67% considered no easy (10%), slightly easy (16%) or moderately easy (41%) the access to these fertilisers.

Figure 32. Importance of producing (a) and the ease of finding (b) circular fertilisers locally.

This fact brings to light that there is a logistic impediment to increase the use of circular fertilisers. This finding is not serendipitous and older studies have already spotted this problem (Case, S. D. C. et. al., 2017).

Figure 33. Economic circumstances to use a circular fertiliser. The * means cheaper, same price or slightly more expensive compared to mineral fertilisers.

Nevertheless, the local access to these fertilisers is not the only obstacle. As previously mentioned, the cost is one of the key factors to select one fertiliser or another (**Table 5**). In this way, another economic question was performed to know the likely a farmer would change a traditional fertiliser by a circular one (**Figure 34**). Farmers would likely use a circular fertiliser instead of a mineral one if the first is subsidized/free of charges or cheaper than the latter (68% of the total). This percentage increases up to 81% whether the price is not higher than the mineral fertilisers. Therefore, this fact is extremely important to achieve the circular economy within the agriculture sector.

Figure 34. Probability of switching to a circular fertiliser.

Finally, a last question to determine the real willingness to use circular fertilisers was performed. As shown in **Figure 34**, 68% of the participants were moderately (42%), slightly (20%) or non-predisposed (6%) to switch from a mineral fertiliser to a circular one. These results suggest that farmers may select circular fertilisers, but only if the price and local availability compete against the mineral ones.

2.1.3.2.4. Conclusions

- Importance of different characteristics of fertilisers when selecting them.
- The performance of fertilisers is represented as the less important factor among surveyors. On the other hand, whether the product is environmentally friendly and sustainable is the most important fact pointed by farmers.
- Fertiliser producers' companies develop products in different forms and try to maintain the current machinery used in the farms. The surveys showed that this transition was carried out properly, showing a lack of nervousness among key stakeholders.
- Strong perception of utility should be used as an advantage of circular fertilisers.
- Subsidies must be economically appealing to attract new adopters to these new products, even if the circular fertiliser is well known by the farmer.

- Participants' concerns
 - Among the four questions blended into the graphs, there was a clear trend to high concern levels in general topics, like the prize of the performance of the product
 - Environmental issues can be addressed by introducing a mandatory label methodology in which performance, footprint and nutrient composition should be clear in order to palliate end-users' concerns.
- Circumstance of choosing a circular fertiliser
 - Farmers are reporting difficulties to find stock of circular fertilisers nearby. Only 34% of the contestant find this task really or extremely easy.
 - Their main interest is to find them locally produced.
 - The 42% of respondents are moderately predisposed to change their current fertiliser to a circular one. In this "indecision interval" is the chance of acceptability by citizens.
 - The huge piece of surveyors that are indecisive shed light on the importance of fostering social acceptance in these circular products

2.1.3.3. NIMBY EFFECT AND SUPPORTING

After evaluating the importance of the local production and an ease access to circular fertilisers, the FER-PLAY Consortium wanted to analyse the NIMBY (Not-In-My-Back-Yard) effect. As its name points out, this effect assesses the willingness of a local community to allow a facility settlement in the surroundings, showing a positive behaviour to a certain type of industry.

To contrast this behavioural attitude, two extra questions were assessed to shell light into the opinion about circular fertilisers and circular economy among surveyors.

2.1.3.3.1. NIMBY effect:

Referring to this topic, 61% of the participants (219 people) were not worried about having a production plant of circular fertilisers near their areas, knowing they come from secondary raw materials (**Figure 35a**). For those people who answered yes (141 people), the survey included a question to know the minimum distance at which the facility settlement would be accepted (**Figure 35b**). A total of 55% ranged their desirable distance between 2 and 15 km far (77 people). Therefore, it may be considered that the surveyed people were not against the implementation of a circular fertiliser plant in the surroundings. This would reduce the logistic impediment mentioned above.

Although most of the surveyors have a positive attitude for industries in the surroundings, it is important to take into account those who do not support them. For sure the finding of a NIMBY effect is not surprising. The possibility to have bad odours in the neighbourhood can influence citizens to refuse circular fertilisers' industries. This effect has already been reported (Case, S. D. C., 2017).

Figure 35. Results obtained of participants about their (A) concerns about having a circular fertiliser factory less than two kilometres from their home and their B) desirable distance to have a circular fertiliser production nearby.

Currently there are several technologies already implanted in waste treatment plants. Deodorisation using biofilters (Biard, P.-F. et. al., 2013) or liquefying the bad odour molecules (Szyłak-Szydłowski, M., & Kulig, A. 2024) are examples of technologies laid down in the waste treatment sector.

Works that are not implanted yet are as well interesting. Xuan Wang et. al. (Wang, X. et. al., 2018) reported a reduction of ammonia and VFAs (volatile fatty acids) by trapping ammonia through struvite formation. This synthesis also improves the microbial activity and therefore the compost formation, as pointed by the authors of the study.

Also, lots of strategies are being studied to reduce odour in the application phase to the field. This is not our purpose here (Orzi, V. et. al., 2018; Ranadheera, C. S. et. al., 2017).

2.1.3.3.2. Opinion about circular fertilisers and circular economy among surveyors.

To continue analysing their possible attitude and support, two questions were conducted to surveyors. They answered based on their agreement with the following two statements:

- The first one asks for rating the inconvenience that the circular fertiliser production could cause and if it is offset by the benefits of circularity that they provide.
- The second one asks for the degree of support to the advantages that circular economy strategies bring into the table.

Both questions show non-well-defined opinions, being the most repeated answer the neutral one: “moderately agree”. Nevertheless, the plots exhibit slightly more adepts than refusers, showing a positive attitude towards circular fertilisers.

In the first question it is important to highlight a small increase in the “slightly disagree” answers to this question, as shown in **Figure 36a**. Therefore, it is important to ensure a minimum environmental and social impact linked to a reliable business model. Impact assessments of circular fertiliser are still scarce, removing legitimacy from the circular benefits that they can provide.

The **Figure 36b** still has lots of undecided voters. Even that approving opinions are way higher than unfavourable ones, circular economy might not be seen as a real alternative to the traditional agricultural system.

Figure 36. Degree of agreement with the idea that a) the inconvenience that circular fertiliser production is offset by the benefits they provide and b) supporting circular fertilisers due to the circular advantages they provide

2.1.3.3.3. Conclusions

- The majority of surveyors do not consider the presence of nearby fertilisers’ industries to be significant. A small NIMBY effect is detected. This fact shows a positive behaviour towards fertiliser companies that manages waste by-products.

- The finding of a NIMBY effect is not surprising due to unpleasant noises and odours generated by waste treatment companies. Extra effort in implementing new technologies should be done by these businesses. On this way the NIMBY effect will be reduced.
- To tackle more specific concerns and reach adepts one option is to foster clusters and technical advisors associations and learning online academies. On that way citizens can freely educate themselves.

2.1.3.4. KNOWLEDGE & TRUSTWORTHINESS

In this section, farmers trustworthiness and their perception of the legislation is exposed. This behaviour is a key to understand the current state of the European farms. The lack of reliable information for stakeholders is understood to be the most typical barrier to market acceptance (Simpson, G. 2018). This phenomenon can be exemplified with the bio-based fertilisers. In the context of circular fertilisers, bio-based fertilisers are products often inoculated with microorganisms. It has been widely demonstrated that these microorganisms can improve soil health, nutrient solubility, and absorption, acting like soil improvers. This type of product has been used by agrarians for decades, but scamming has been frequent. For these reasons is normal to find lack of trust for producers (Olsen, P.E. et. al., 1996).

2.1.3.4.1. Level of awareness of law

In the present studio, the lack of awareness regarding fertilisers' legislation is reflected in 48.9% of farmers, who declare check updates less than once per year. Among contestants, 35% answer that are in touch with the national legislation, followed by 30% that checks regional legislation and 11% that checks European legislation. Only 11% check the three areas. These numbers exposed in **Figure 37** show that farmers might not be comfortable.

Figure 37. Percentage of respondents that check any level of regulation at least once per year

In total, €387 billion of funding has been allocated to the CAP (Common Agricultural Policy) as part of the EU's long-term budget, the multiannual financial framework (2021–2027). The European Green Deal is the EU's strategy for sustainable growth. It aims to turn climatic and environmental challenges into opportunities for a broad range of policy areas. The Green Deal aims to make Europe the first climate-neutral continent by 2050. The CAP plays a part in this transition, as approximately 40 % of its budget is climate relevant.

In 2016, the EU Commission published a draft of a new regulation to boost the use of organic waste-based fertiliser. Until now, the regulation law of circular fertiliser based on waste by-products as a raw material has not been established. This might be a point to improve consumers' awareness of these products, allowing them to be introduced in the market with the strong help of the scientific community, such as developing more toxicological analysis or blends of different products.

Farmers might not be comfortable with implementing the specific objectives of the Common Agriculture Policy.

Figure 38. The level of regulation the respondents check.

Regarding the level of awareness of surveyors, farmers find national institutions the most reliable one (35%). As well, 30% of respondents check regional legislation. These percentages are way higher than the 11% that check the EU law or the 11% that examine the three mentioned levels.

2.1.3.4.2. Trustworthiness along the farmers.

One of the most important aspects extracted from the survey is trustworthiness. Respondents were invited to answer in a five-point Likert scale the trustworthiness of eight key value-chain actors: specialised press, neighbouring farmer, farmers' association, fertiliser producers, salespersons, environmental NGOs, technical advisors, and public authorities. By evaluating the reliance of end users on their environment, miscellaneous ideas are extracted.

- In general, farmers have moderate trustworthiness in their neighbours, fluctuating notably among countries and types of farming.
- Farmers' associations are trustworthy sources but still vary notably in the studio.
- The most fixed and reliable sources were technical advisors and specialised press. However, salespersons and NGOs were the most discredited.
- Based on consortium knowledge, fertiliser producers already detect farmers do not trust sales representatives. To solve this problem, the fertiliser industry is hiring external technical advisors.

- The fact that NGOs are underrated in this classification may be explained by the perception of stakeholders that these organisations are disconnected from the real world.
- Public authorities have a bad reputation, disrupting key conflictive voting processes during election periods. These institutions are becoming involved in coordinating and supporting action projects, working among real users' problems, and reaching reliability among them.

The extracted numerical data are shown in Table 6.

Table 6. Trustworthiness among respondents about: specialised press, neighbours, farmers associations, fertiliser producers, salespersons, NGOs, technical advisors and public authorities.

	Non-trustworthy	Slightly trustworthy	Moderate trustworthy	Very trustworthy	Extremely trustworthy
Specialized press	7.2%	15.3%	43.6%	31.7%	1.9%
Neighbour farmer	7.3%	19.6%	52.0%	15.9%	5.3%
Farmers association	5.3%	20.8%	38.9%	21.4%	13.3%
Fertiliser producers	8.9%	21.1%	43.9%	23.1%	2.5%
Salesperson	11.4%	30.1%	49.3%	8.4%	0.3%
Environment NGOs	15.9%	19.8%	50.7%	11.4%	2.2%
Technical advisors	0.8%	10.6%	44.3%	30.3%	14.0%
Public authorities	6.2%	22.1%	40.8%	27.9%	3.1%

Where citizens place their trust is been a widely studied topic. The European project CONCISE (Communication role on perception and beliefs of EU Citizens about Science) study trustful communication channels tackling different topics: vaccines, complementary and alternative medicine (CAM), climate change and genetically modified organisms (GMOs). Their analysis revealed plenty of trust in public authorities and NGOs. Commercial companies were not considered a trustful source of information (Commission, E. 2024).

Based on the engaging scientific communication Eu project TRESKA (trustworthy, Reliable and Engaging Scientific Communication Approaches): "a lot of public trust is based on the credibility that you give to certain organisations," says Jason Pridmore, TRESKA project coordinator. "You're more likely to trust an organisation if somebody in your general social network trusts them, which is also how misinformation can spread," he explains (Commission, E. 2024). This idea is verified by Garmendia-Lemus et al. (2024), who detected that social network and experts' acceptance are crucial configuring end-user's perception of circular fertilisers (Li, J., & Xu, X. 2023).

2.1.3.4.3. Conclusions

- Pressure from governmental legislation was identified as a key stimulant of technology adoption for Circular fertilisers production.
- Authors like Kurniawati et al. (2023) supports that incentives to complement the new fertiliser product regulation (FPR) should come from regional institutions.
- Similarly, as fertiliser producers hire external technical advisors, the EU should keep clustering private companies that work as technical consultancy firms.
- Fertiliser producers and salespersons are not perceived as a fair communication channel among farmers. This fact should be fixed along the time. One short-term idea for producers is to outsourced external advisors to ensure a proper communication with end users.
- NGOs are not perceived as a neutral stakeholder.

2.2. Social acceptance discussion

Social acceptance is a well-known concept defined as a trend in different levels of society - e.g. country, region, community, organisations - in different cognitive states - that is, perception, opinion, attitudes, and behaviours - intertwined with a technology or technical system (Upham et al., 2015; Wolsink, 2010). Using the explained methodology explained in section 1.1.2 , the authors proceed to carry out the discussion of the social acceptance of circular fertilisers among farmers.

2.2.1. Socio-political acceptance

2.2.1.1. STRONG INSTITUTIONAL CAPACITY

What are the perceptions of farmers about political institutions?

In line with the strong institutional capacity, policymakers are developing a negative social acceptance. There is a general lack of trustworthiness in public administration: the 28% shows mistrust and the 41%, keeps neutral. This leads to an arguable opinion of these institutions.

Farmers do not feel that current politicians are a reliable source, as the 49% do not check the law. One reason that might influence this action is the scarcity of the local feedstock, as the one quarter of the contestants show concern about the fact that is tough to find local feedstock.

End users regret the circular products based on this subsection. A clear negative opinion leads to a negative attitude.

2.2.1.2. POLITICAL COMMITMENT

Are the communication channels among farmers an institution beneficial?

Not many political commitments can be found in the survey.

Contestants do not check all legal levels (only 11% do it), delimiting the power of these institutions. This is an unnatural point regarding the positive social perception of circular fertilisers. The inability of policymakers to develop an optimal communication channel might be due to a hitherto distrust atmosphere among workers. Examples attached are:

- A negative perception of excessive control of laws, as Mariano Zapata (leader of Proexport, a senior agriculture company in Spain, with more than 25.000 employees) postulates in the 2024 strikes arguing that: “we have a huge number of normative and bureaucracy that are absolutely asphyxiating for the agrarian sector”.
- Long waiting slots for promised laws, like MEMO/16/826 or the new fertilising product regulation, which is supposed to include new labelling of bio-waste-based fertilisers.
- Unexpected block of the voting procedure of environmental laws like the corporate sustainable due diligence directive (CSDDD).

Assessment of the surveys leads to a non-well-defined answer to the question of whether communication channels among farmers and institutions are profitable. In general, the authors did not reject circular fertilisers based on this subcategory. Nevertheless, negative attitudes are linked to negative opinions.

European projects act as a liaison between value chain actors, being on the writer's opinion, the shortest path to start reaching a positive dynamic of acceptance in the socio-political frame; starting making a topic highly visible.

2.2.2. Market

2.2.2.1. COMPETITIVE PROPERTIES OF THE NEW PRODUCTS

Are farmers' concerns and preferences addressed by the market?

The availability of technical information about circular fertilisers against synthetic ones is a crucial consideration for competitiveness. Among the surveyors, the most repeated fertiliser is manure,

a circular fertiliser. With this data the writers want to highlight the widespread use of these products. The most common trend is not to substitute the current fertilisers for a circular option but to merge them (Melkamu Jate 2022; Frederik van der Bom 2017).

One of the key challenges is the cost and availability of organic fertilisers (Egan, 2022). They are often more expensive and difficult to obtain than synthetic ones. Based on the consortium farmers network, agrarian workers sometimes do not have full availability of compost and spent mushroom substrate. Compost is a widespread circular fertiliser with a production of 60,000 Tonnes per year in the European union (based on data provided by A.S.A.J.A) but still does not fit the market's request. Spent mushroom substrate issue is remarkable: it is produced in big amounts (based on data provided by A.S.A.J.A) but, even that farmers demand it, it is only locally consumed. More supply will be expected if social acceptance rises.

The most frequent circumstances to be willing to use circular fertilisers have been found to be related to taxes and subsidies. Economical subsidise must continue.

2.2.2.2. MECHANISMS OF INFORMATION AND FEEDBACK

Are farmers' communication channels with institutions and circular fertiliser producers reliable?

The fairness of communication channels is arguable. In 2023, researchers reported a threshold exceedance plastic mass in circular fertilisers (Estoppey, N., et. al. 2024). In the context of circular fertilisers, bio-based fertilisers are products often inoculated with microorganisms that boost soil quality (Maitra, S. et. al., 2021). Among other effects, they improve nutrient absorption. This type of product has been used for agrarians for decades, but scamming has been frequenting in the past (Olsen, P.E. et. al., 1996; Olsen, P.E. et. al., 1995). For these reasons, it is normal to find a lack of trust for end-users and, therefore, policymakers who cannot regulate laws about pertinent quality analysis.

The current Fertiliser Product and amending Regulation (FPR) 2019/1009 was settled after a long waiting period. Farmers were waiting for three years, since the MEMO/16/826 promised a boost in organic and waste-based fertilisers (E. 2023). In June 2021, the EC confirm that "from summer 2022 onwards, fertiliser producers, traders and farmers are confronted with the EU Fertilizing Products Regulation (FPR), which radically changes the way fertilisers are receiving the CE mark and the labelling requirements provided on the products", inform Fertiliser Europe (Fertilizing Products Regulation - Fertilizers Europe). In 2024, these regulations are not ready yet due to an absence of notified bodies and the fact that harmonised testing methods have not yet been published. Although the European Compost Network (ECN) concluded in 2022 that 25% of all compost produced accomplishes a quality assurance scheme, the EU still does not develop a proper market regulatory for these types of circular products.

To fill this gap, the EU is boosting projects involving living labs. In this pilot farms, new products were publicly tested. Legitimacy is expected to intertwine these public tests and a strong techno-economical studio with toxicological analysis. No effort will be worth it if the current regulation does not fit the mercantile standards.

2.2.2.3. ACCESS TO SUBSIDIES

Do the farmers feel the necessity of subsidizing these products?

The survey clearly showed that farmers perceived the necessity of subsidise. Fertiliser prices have increased worldwide since the end of 2021. In this context, the value of organic fertilisers has changed from the farmers' perspective (Daadi, B. E., & Latacz-Lohmann, U. 2021)

Up to 2024, the risk of fertilisers producers' facilities relocation is astonishingly high (Egan A. et. al., 2022). Moving those industries outside Europe allow these companies to reduce the manufacturing cost. This action sometimes involves a reduction in quality controls. It is important to take this into account when selecting which stakeholders will receive funds.

CAP involves several proposals to address circular solutions for farms. In total, €387 billions of funding has been allocated to the CAP as part of the EU's long-term budget, the multiannual financial framework (2021–2027) (Agriculture statistics at regional level - Statistics Explained. 2023). Even in the above-mentioned living labs, the EU subsidise part of the detrimental effects of the harvest, if any.

On a qualitative approach, the writers consider that the current access to funds match the agrarian workers' perception of a necessity of subsidizing. This synergy will lead to a positive acceptance of circular fertiliser.

2.2.3. Community

2.2.3.1. PROLIFIC COMMUNITY/INDIVIDUAL OWNERSHIP AND USE

Will farmers purchase local circular fertilisers on their business?

The number of circular fertilisers cannot compete with the huge variety of mineral ones offered in the current market. Nevertheless, many farmers choose the circular options due to their interesting properties. Extra efforts in fostering properties and parameters desired by farmer must be done. Farmers tend to use fertilisers with texture and characteristics similar to the mineral options (Tur-Cardona, J. et. al., 2018). Therefore, circular fertilisers that accomplish those characteristics have to be up lifted.

Positive perceptions and opinions were found among surveyors. When the consortium evaluated attitudes, negative trends were revealed, as the NIMBY condition found revealed. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight a rejection in this subsection.

2.2.3.2. PUBLIC PARTICIPATION IN POLICYMAKING

Will farmers introduce legal trends to local agricultural policies?

The contestants' answers reveal a willingness to boost the local focus. Nearby products are demanded so, in the author's opinion, participatory project siting with local stakeholders is an important issue to address. Scientists like Egan (2022) rises the idea that farmers do not understand the decision-making process. This lack of knowledge produce can be solved by involving end-users and policymakers.

Negative attitudes were observed in the previous subsection due to the NIMBY effect. Involving local key stakeholders in the legal procedure and making part of the development of policies and strategies might be a crucial point to address in order to solve that problem.

2.2.3.3. RECOGNITION OF EXTERNALITIES OR POSITIVE PUBLIC IMAGE

Do farmers perceive these products as goods?

There are more allies of circular fertiliser than oppositions; there are 32% of adepts against 26% of opposites according to the question of probability to switch to a circular product. Their perception of risks about the situation of soils and the environmental impact of mineral fertilisers leads them to a slightly proactive attitude. This is like that because due to this concern about soil health, farmers show the attitude to try circular fertilisers and the support to them. However, the survey results are not promising. The differences between good and bad insights are negligible.

Although the majority of contestants answer with indifference towards the goods of circular fertilisers, the remaining ones recognise the strong points of those products.

In the writers' opinion, this subsection is clearly intertwined with the "Political commitment" and the "Mechanisms for information and feedback". Both subsections are promising and boost each other. A strong impact on the recognition of externalities regarding the positive public image will be achieved if this "indifferent" contestants that answer the questions with "moderately agree" can be pleased.

2.3. Legitimacy discussion

Legitimacy theory may vary according to the sector and the specific studio case. In the present document, authors adapt Harris-Lovett's conscious work on the valorisation of potable water reuse in a circular economy frame to the circular fertilisers case, based on the original paper of W. Richard Scott's 1995 "institutions and organisations". For the present document, the authors use the methodology exposed in section 1.1.2.

2.3.1. Pragmatic

2.3.1.1. EXCHANGE

Are circular fertilisers ready to foster soil quality or farmers' concerns?

One of the main concerns among farmers is the ease of use and cost of circular fertilisers. Other preoccupations are nutrient composition, sustainability of the process or necessity of new machinery and product formats.

At first sight, circular products cannot compete with traditional ones because the last ones have honing industrial processes. Nevertheless, circular alternatives address other concerns, such as the optimisation of the contamination generated during the production and transport stages of this industrial processes.

The Farmers do not sense as problematic the machinery and form used in new alternatives. TRLs of new products are very high, supporting farmers' opinions about the fact that these new circular fertilisers will have an easy ease of use and probably without the necessity of purchase new machinery.

With the ongoing status of technology in the fertiliser sector, circular alternatives are ready to solve the detriment in soil quality. Although their performance is lower in general, scientist already post that the correct mindset is to mix circular and mineral products, as the long-term trials shows with manure (Jate & Lammel, 2022). With this mix, farmers will achieve proper yields in addition to other qualities like soil-improving qualities.

2.3.1.2. DISPOSITIONAL

Is public administration fair? What about NGOs and farmers associations?

The survey's results clearly show generalised suspicion. NGOs are the second most distrusted source, and public authorities have moderate trust in society.

2.3.2. Cognitive

2.3.2.1. COMPREHENSIVE

Do circular fertilisers offer an easy transition in terms of training and legal limitations?

In this subsection, a lack of knowledge among contestants is found. This situation is especially hazardous, because assuming legitimacy due to ignorance makes this fairness fragile and irregular. Nevertheless, this section evaluates cultural beliefs and compliance with taken-for-granted routines.

In the test conducted in the survey, the question with the largest number of incorrect answers was related to the possibility of training required for a correct application. The correct answer is circular fertilisers due to their difficulty in applying and their affection for external conditions, among others. Only 31% of the contestants hit the mark.

Circular alternatives for mineral fertilisers offer a huge variety of improvements (O'Donnell et. al., 2022; Barzee et. al., 2019; Egan et. al., 2022). Those enhancements turn into solutions to current farming problems. It is crucial to keep addressing farmers with easy reports and documents that disseminate reliable information to engage in more legitimacy in order to reduce, e.g., the lack of knowledge about the decision-making process found by Egan (2022).

2.3.2.2. TAKEN-FOR-GRANTED LEGITIMACY.

Is there any other option than circular fertilisers to improve soil quality?

Indeed, this subsection is one of the most promising ones for boost legitimacy (Harris-Lovett, S. R. et. al., 2015). Once a product or technology acquires legitimacy, it is difficult to delete it from the society. The feeling that there is no alternative works in favour of engagement.

Figure 39. Degree of agreement with the idea that a) the inconveniences of circular fertilisers production is offset by the benefits they provide; and b) the idea of supporting circular fertilisers due to their circular advantages is a good option.

Looking at the results shown in **Figure 39**, most constants answer positively to take part of this transition towards circular fertilisers options.

There are products improving soil quality and enhancing the performance of crops. Examples are products such as bio stimulants. These products are in pipeline business mode. Solving mineral fertilisers impact with bio-stimulants may solve the soil quality, but in economy related issues, citizens may feel like this means solving one problem creating another. For this reason, the consortium pushes towards circular alternatives, taking advantage of their bigger taken-for-granted legitimacy.

2.3.3. Normative

2.3.3.1. PROCEDURAL

Are public administrations and producers developing business strategies according to the necessity of subsidies?

Several European projects are developing business models in order to make high valuable production chains. Circular goods extracted will provide meaningful characteristics to farmers.

Only 3.6% of the contestants will be willing to change if the circular alternative includes a slightly more expensive prize. This means that, if they fit on their budget, the procedural legitimacy will be considered as positive.

2.3.3.2. STRUCTURAL

Can farmers' concerns be solved by the current status of the solutions provided by the producers?

Currently, there are very few long trials on circular fertilisers. Scientists strive to test as many new circular fertilisers as possible. Toxicological assessments, detection of specific chemical compounds (such as certain types of microplastics) and other tests are being carried out.

Among the European authorities, new policies are not flowing, and scientific findings are still emerging. As a response, fertiliser producers and farmer associations are developing their own quality labels, as in the case of the Italian Compost Consortium (CIC) is doing with composting.

This heterogeneous and immature scenario results in an insecure frame. Deeper assess is needed to evaluate structural legitimacy. Due to this, the subsection will be assessed as neutral.

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fer ▶ play

A stylized logo for 'fer ▶ play' where the 'er' is in black, a green triangle points right, and 'play' is in black. A wheat stalk is integrated into the 'y', growing from a small mound of brown soil.

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